

INTERFACIAL ADHESION AND FATIGUE RESISTANCE OF POLYKETONE/ RUBBER COMPOSITE

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1. Introduction

Rayon, nylon, and polyester fibers have been used for a long time as general reinforcements of rubber composites. Recently, application of the para-aramid fiber which has high tenacity and modulus is gradually increasing in order to satisfy high performance requirements, large tires, and tire weight reduction. However, in working with high strength and modulus fibers like para-aramid it is normally difficult to obtain an excellent adhesion with simple processing and their fatigue resistances is not good [1].

Newly developed polyketone fiber is available by copolymerization of carbon monoxide and unsaturated hydrocarbon monomer, ethylene. Hence, the cost of its raw material is very cheap and the spinning process is environmental-friendly. Also, it has the additional benefits of similar tenacity and modulus to para-aramid, and has higher breaking elongation, and good adhesion property with a rubber matrix. Therefore, it is expected to apply it to the reinforcement of mechanical rubber goods (MRG) such as tires, hoses and protective gloves [2].

Various fiber cords are used as rubber reinforcements of automotive tires. Adhesion strength between textile cord materials and rubber matrix can affect performance of a tire. To improve interfacial adhesion between polar cord and nonpolar rubber, an adhesive agent must be used [3, 4]. Since 1935, resorcinol-formaldehyde-latex (RFL) has been used to promote the cord/rubber adhesion. Generally, textile cord must be coated in RFL dip followed by pre-curing. Low viscosity and good wetting properties have advantages of these aqueous dips. After curing, they are transformed to an insoluble system. The latex gives required flexibility to adhesive agent and reactivity to rubber. Moreover, RF resin provides a desirable heat and fatigue resistance by forming a three-dimensional network [5-15].

At cord/rubber interface, the functional groups of polar cord and unsaturated zones of rubber undergo reactions with methylol and vinyl groups of RFL, respectively [16-17]. Physical forces originated from interpenetration and interlocking of the RF resin with

the fiber can be a major factor of adhesion, as well [18-21].

The purpose of this study is to improve the interfacial adhesion between polyketone cord and natural rubber (NR) by applying the RFL adhesive primer. To measure the adhesion strength between polyketone cord and rubber, the H-test and micro-droplet debonding test were performed. In order to evaluate the fatigue resistance of polyketone cord/rubber composite, the tension-compression fatigue test was conducted. To estimate the surface changes and adhesion properties of the RFL-coated-polyketone cord, various instrumental analysis were performed including attenuated total reflectance (ATR)-IR.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Rubber compound

Composition of the natural rubber used in this study is given in Table 1. Same formulation was used in all experiments. Materials were weighed and mixed in an internal mixer and rolled in a roll mill. Finally, they were changed to a sheet with thickness of 6 mm.

Table 1. Composition of rubber compound

Component	Weight (g)
NR	170
Topping #1	200
ZnO	35
DP-805	1.4
Stearic Acid	7
SRF	105
Zeosil #155	21
CaCO ₃	400
A #2	56
Anti. Ble-N	7
Rosin	21
Acc. DM	8.4
Acc. CZ	2.1

2.1.2 Fiber

The molecular structure of polyketone fiber is shown in Fig.1. In this study, polyketone fiber was supplied from “H” company in Korea. Table.2 shows the properties of the fiber used in this study.

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of polyketone fiber

Table 2. Properties of polyketone fiber

Fineness (denier)	Strength (g/denier)	Elongation (%)
747	15	6.0

2.1.3 Cord

Polyketone cord was prepared through the two-for-one twister from polyketone fiber supplied. Table.3 shows the twis per meter(TPM) condition of the polyketone cord.

Table 3. Conditions of twisting of polyketone cord

TPM	502	684	760	868
Direction of twist	S	S	S	S
	↓			
TPM	251	342	380	434
Direction of twist	Z	Z	Z	Z

2.2 Surface treatment

Polyketone cords were washed with acetone by using ultrasonic agitation for 1 hour. Then, they were washed with distilled water repeatedly. After purifying polyketone cord, their surfaces were treated with a primer consisted with RFL and epoxy. Typical formulation of the RFL is given in Table 4. In surface treatment, processing conditions such as

dipping time, adhesive pick-up ratio and heating temperature were varied. Primer dipping process of the polyketone cord is schematically shown in Fig.2.

Table 4. Typical formulation of the RFL adhesive

	Wet part (g)
RF solution	
Resorcinol	16
Formaldehyde	7
Sodium hydroxide	1
Water	200
Maturation: 25°C, 4h	224
Final dip solution	
RF solution	224
Latex	160
Ammonium hydroxide	5
Water	120
Maturation: 25°C, 12h	509
Epoxy (1, 3, 6, 9, 12 weight %)	

Fig.2 Schematics of the primer dipping process

2.3 Thermal properties

Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, 2010DSC TA instruments) was used to investigate thermal properties of polyketone fiber. Samples were scanned at heating rates of 5°C/min, in the temperature range of 20-300°C. Nitrogen was used as a purge gas.

2.4 Surface characterization

A fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR, Bruker Optic GmbH, ALPHA-P) equipped with an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory was used to examine the surface composition of the polyketone cord. The spectra were recorded in the transmission mode in the range of 4000-500cm⁻¹.

FT-IR spectra were measured at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and the spectra were obtained with an accumulation of 128 scans for a high signal-to-noise ratio.

Also, morphological changes of polyketone fibers were observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM, S4700, HITACHI) with surface treatment condition.

2.5 Interfacial adhesion tests

The interfacial adhesion properties were measured with the H-test method according to the ASTM D4776. To prepare the H-test samples, rubber sheets were placed in the channels of a stainless steel die. Then, the surface treated cord was embedded in rubber sheets. The shape of the sample and test set-up are shown in Fig.3. Samples were vulcanized at 160°C , for 30min. at pressure of 48MPa. Then the products were cut into H-shape samples.

Test was performed by using an Instron 4467 tester under room temperature and the cross-head speed was fixed at 125mm/min. Adhesion strength was calculated from the maximum load.

Fig.3 Preparation of the H-test: (a) the H-test sample, (b) photo of test set-up (ASTM D4776)

In addition, the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between the polyketone fiber and rubber was measured by the micro-droplet debonding test by using an Instron (model 4467). The micro-droplet debonding test has been widely used to evaluate the interfacial shear strength for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites. The fiber specimen was suspended at one end of a load cell of a mechanical

machine and the micro-droplet was gripped by the microvise jaws mounted on the other stationary end of the tester. Test was performed at the cross-head speed of 1 mm/min under room temperature.

The maximum force (F_{\max}) was recorded to calculate the interfacial shear strength (τ_{\max}) using equation (1):

$$\tau_{\max} = F_{\max} / \pi DL \quad (1)$$

Where, D and L are fiber diameter and fiber embedded length, respectively.

2.6 Fatigue resistance

The tension-compression fatigue properties of the polyketone cord were measured using molded composite samples (Fig.4) in a micro material tester. The fatigue resistance was tested with a fatigue tester according to the ASTM D6588. Tests were performed at 120°C and test cycle times were 8, 12, 24, and 48hours. The force loss (FL) of each sample was calculated by using an equation (2):

$$FL = ((B-A)/B) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where, A and B are the average breaking force of fatigued cords and that of unfatigued cords, respectively.

Fig.4 Schematics of the sample set-up for fatigue test

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile properties

The results of the tensile test of the polyketone cord are given in Fig.5. It was observed that the breaking strength (tenacity) decreased and breaking elongation increased with the TPM range between 251 and 434. It is well known that when the twist is applied to any textile yarn, the breaking strength of the yarn increases initially up to an optimum TPM, and then decreases independent type of materials [22-23]. Due to this reason, a cord with higher TPM has lower breaking strength and higher fatigue resistance. Therefore, in order to obtain better fatigue resistance and breaking strength, the TPM of tire cord must be kept in a certain range.

Fig.5 Tensile properties of polyketone cord with different TPM

3.2 Thermal properties of polyketone fiber

Fig.6 shows the DSC curve of polyketone cord. The melting point of polyketone fiber was about 265°C.

Fig.6 DSC result of polyketone fiber

3.3 Interfacial adhesion strength

3.3.1 H-test

Fig.7 shows the adhesion strength from H-test results according to TPM. The results showed the highest adhesion strength at 380 TPM. However, excessive twist (434 TPM) showed the lowest adhesion strength because the excessive twist obstructed a rubber permeate to the polyketone fiber.

Fig.7 Adhesion strength according to the TPM of polyketone cord

Fig.8 shows H-test results according to dipping time of the cord. Dipping time in RFL solution is related to the adhesive pick-up ratio in a tire cord. Adhesion strength increased with dipping time because of an increase of the pick-up ratio of adhesive. However, excessive pick-up caused a decrease of adhesion strength because it brings about hardness of polyketone cord. From the results of the H-test (Fig.8), optimum dipping time was 3min. It was considered that the excessive dipping time caused a decrease of adhesion strength.

Fig.8 H-test results according to dipping time (dip-RFL)

Fig.9 shows the H-test results of polyketone cord according to heating temperature. The highest adhesion strength was obtained at 240°C because a cross-linked network was formed during reaction of the appropriate heating temperature. However, adhesion strength decreased over than heating temperature of 240°C because excessive formation of the cross-linked structure with large reactive molecules might cause a brittle fracture of the interface.

Fig.9 H-test results according to heating temperature (dip-RFL)

Fig.10 shows adhesion strength of the cord with the epoxy content in RFL solution. As increasing epoxy content, adhesion strength increased too. However, both 12% and 9% showed similar strengths. It was considered that the adhesion strength was almost not changed with the epoxy content over than 9%.

Fig.10 H-test results according to epoxy content (dip-RFL + epoxy)

3.3.2 Micro-droplet debonding test

In this test, a small amount of liquid rubber was dabbed on to the fiber surface. After the resin droplet was cured, an elliptical concentric micro-droplet was formed around the fiber. The interfacial shear strength between polyketone fiber and rubber was determined with the micro-droplet debonding test results. Fig.11 shows the IFSS results with primer composition. As a result, the IFSS of polyketone fiber showed the highest adhesion strength when using RFL/epoxy (9%).

Fig.11 IFSS results according to primer treatment

3.4 Surface characteristics of RFL coated polyketone cord

Fig.12 shows the ATR spectra of RFL coated polyketone cord. When the heating temperature increased from 230°C to 250°C, results of the ATR analysis showed a tendency to decrease in both methylol peak at 1,092 cm^{-1} and resorcinol peak at 1,164 cm^{-1} . Also, 4, 6-hydroxymethyl resorcinol peak at 889 and 975 cm^{-1} decreased. From the result, 240°C was an optimum processing temperature with preferable surface chemistry of the cord.

Fig.12 ATR spectra of RFL coated polyketone cord

3.5 Morphological observation

Fig.13 shows surface morphology after the H-test of raw polyketone cord and 380 TPM condition. The RFL coated polyketone cord shows a morphological view of the primer diffusion into the cord surface compared with the raw polyketone cord. As increasing primer DPU(dip pick up) ratio, penetration of the primer into the polyketone fiber bundle increased.

(a)

(b)

Fig.13 SEM micrographs of the surface of the polyketone cord after the H-test: (a) Raw, (b) 380 TPM

Fig.14 shows a cross-sectional morphology after the H-test of raw polyketone cord and 380 TPM having maximum adhesion strength. RFL coated polyketone

cord shows that the penetration and uniform distribution of the rubber inside the cord.

(a)

(b)

Fig.14 Cross sectional view of the polyketone cord after the H-test: (a) Raw, (b) 380 TPM

3.3 Fatigue properties

Results of tension-compression fatigue test of the polyketone cord/rubber composite were summarized in Table 5. Fatigue resistance of the polyketone cord increased with an increase of adhesion strength (Fig.8-10). However, a cord coated with RFL/epoxy (9%) had a lower fatigue resistance than those of a cord coated with RFL because the addition of epoxy caused a hard nature of the cord. Consequently, high fatigue resistance was obtained with high adhesion strength.

Table.5 Fatigue resistances of polyketone cord/rubber composite after tension-compression fatigue at different TPMs

Fatigue time (h)	Samples				
	RFL coated (240°C, 3 min)				RFL+epoxy (9%) coated (240°C, 3 min)
	Fatigue resistance (%)				
	251 TPM	342 TPM	380 TPM	434 TPM	380 TPM
8	97.0	97.5	98.2	97.2	97.4
12	93.1	93.4	95.5	93.3	93.7

4. Conclusions

In this study, surface of the polyketone cord was coated by primers in order to improve the interfacial strength with a rubber. The surface chemical composition and morphological properties of the polyketone cord were changed by the primer treatment. With the experimental results, following conclusions were obtained.

- The highest adhesion strength of the cord was obtained with a twist condition of 380 TPM.
- From the analysis of ATR spectra of the RFL coated polyketone cord, heating temperature of 240°C was the optimum condition with preferable surface chemistry.
- From the results of the H-test and micro-droplet debonding test, RFL/epoxy (9%) coated sample utilizing 380 TPM had maximum adhesion strength.
- RFL coated polyketone cord showed a morphological view of the primer diffusion into the cord surface compared with the raw polyketone cord.
- With the results of fatigue test, fatigue resistance increased as adhesion strength increased.

Consequently, the interfacial adhesion properties between the polyketone cord and rubber increased largely with the primer treatment.

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